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Monolithic Earthen Shells and Robotic Fabrication

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1 Perforated earthen shells. Third layer of clay mix being sprayed robotically. This additive manufacturing technique allows freeform structures. IAAC Seminar 2016.

This project explores the implementation of additive manufacturing for monolithic shells based on the deposition of different clay mixes through robotic spraying over a temporary fabric formwork. The framework sits at the intersection of ancient construction traditions, digital modelling techniques, and robotic control protocols.

Raw mud can be found in ancient construction traditions, from mud huts to wattle and daub techniques, to the recent appearance of 3d printed extrusions in several academic research projects. Thin shell vaulting has relevant precedents throughout the 20th century, incorporating a variety of formwork methods for spray concrete ranging from pneumatics to fabrics to the recent fabric removable formwork and metal mesh reinforcement for robotic spray concrete (Veenendaal and Block, 2014).

This highly sustainable project is actively implementing the principle of “resistance through form” (Eladio Dieste, 1996) at the design stage, by using geometries with curvatures that result in active surfaces that are optimized and tested in 3d modelling softwares (Rhino, Grasshopper and Karamba).

Robotic actions prove crucial to facilitate the laborious tasks associated with traditional craft techniques, providing control for the deposition of the correct thickness and homogeneity of the

2 Seminar IAAC 2017. 3D scan performed through Agisoft and simplified in Rhino

3 Fabric and branches formwork removal. Smart Geometry workshop 2016

4 Various robotically sprayed earthen shells of 1 x 1 x 70 m. IAAC Workshop 2016.

different clay mixes, allowing recalibrations according to matter changing properties (i.e. level of viscosity, humidity), permitting adjustments on the deformations and displacements experienced during depositions. The contribution of the earthen monolithic shell project lies in being the only robotically sprayed clay research on a temporary fabric formwork seeking a full-scale prototype.

Physical experiments have successfully resulted in the construction of several 2 m high shell prototypes with 3cm thickness, implemented in workshops such as the Smart Geometry, AA visiting schools (Lyon 2012-2015), and IAAC seminars (2015-2017). During the experiments, a precise iterative protocol was implemented, consisting in sequential loops for placement, consolidation, and finishing. The placement stage starts with a stretched fabric supported by a series of bending arches, followed by fitting the robotic arm with a series of conventional construction paint sprayer nozzles that deposit different types of clay mixes. During several stages of the deposition, iterative 3D

scans are conducted to provide updated readings on the shell's evolution and to identify suitable thicknesses for each layer.

A digital mesh informs the continuous shell optimization by highlighting tension, compression, and problematic areas. A constant recalibration of the robotic spray provides adjustments in the settings driving the robotic trajectories (KUKA prc) that control the path, pressure, speed, and deposition angle. The consolidation stage deposits clay mixes high in fibres to reach appropriate thickness while providing a lightweight reinforcement. The finish loop includes the removal by hand of the temporary formwork and concludes with the final robotic application of natural stabilizers.

5 Top: Detail of robotically poured natural resin embedded in earthen shells. Bottom: Parrot drone projecting mini balls on earthen shell in progress. IAAC Workshop 2017

6 Parrot drone 3D scanning of the earthen shell in progress. IAAC 2017

7 Continuous robotic spraying, KUKA prc simulation. Smart Geometry 2016.

8 Karamba/Rhino stress lines analysis for reinforcement.

9 Earthen shell thickness variation according to tension or compression zones

This technique currently seeks further degrees of automation for architectural scale implementation. Active bending for the formwork frames could insert the support rods in the fabric and robotically scan and bend the arches. Reinforcement strips could be robotically placed in specific locations with variations according to stress lines and changing structural conditions during fabrication. Real time 3D scanning can expand with the use of drone flight control (on site or remote), facilitating a series of fast decision-making options during the fabrication process. Current work involves increasing the interactivity between the material deposition process and monitoring by working with agricultural drone companies to perform 3D scans (photogrammetric, thermal), at the same time evaluating the drone's load capacity to carry the clay mix and perform the spray. Augmented reality devices are also being explored to show the structure's distortion in real time linked to robotic actions, opening unique features for earthen monolithic shell fabrication.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research forms part of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, ITN Innochain, grant number #642877.

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10 Concrete hand sprayer as Agkus KUKA Robot end effector used to spray middle fibrous layers of the earthen shells. Smart Geometry 2016

11 Resin robotically poured on wet earthen shell. IAAC 2017

12 Augmented reality experiment showing earthen shell deformations, IAAC 2017

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IMAGE CREDITS

Photos credits 1-12 by workshop's participants

Stephanie Chaltiel Originally from France, Stephanie has over 10 years experience as an architect. Stephanie has worked for Bernard Tschumi in New York (Elliptic City- IFCA-2006), For OMA in Paris (Monaco Extension on the water- 2008), and for Zaha Hadid in London (Pierres Vives Construction – 2010). Stephanie also has valuable experience in countries such as Mexico, and French Guyana, applying sustainable materials and techniques for housing solutions. Stephanie has been teaching in France and in London, at SUTD in Singapore and currently at IAAC Barcelona. Stephanie has also been directing the AA (Architectural Association) Visiting School in Lyon which has investigated and explored the use of digital technologies in conjunction with earth construction. She is currently a Marie Curie researcher and PhD candidate investigating the potential of combining small robotics with earth architecture principles.

Maité Bravo Architect from the University of Chile (FAU UCh), Master of Advanced Architecture (IAAC), and Master in Theory and Practice of Architectural Design (ETSAB-UPC). She obtained a PhD International Mention with a "Cum Laude" distinction at the UPC Architectural Design Department, studying concepts and design methodologies emerging from the use of parametric digital design and its immersion into the architectural praxis. Her academic experience includes the University of Chile (UCh), the British Columbia Institute of Technology (BCIT Canada), and IAAC since 2008. She has been a visiting professor at ETH Zürich, and a guest lecturer or jury member at several international universities. She is currently the academic coordinator of the IAAC-Urban Sciences Lab, the co-director of the IAAC Theory for Advanced Knowledge Group (TAK), and faculty for several courses at IAAC.